

Governance in Nonprofit Organizations: A Literature Review

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Introduction

The aim of this work is to explore the importance of governance within a nonprofit organization, the key features commonly ascribed to effective governance, and the impact of governance on the operations of a nonprofit organization as represented in a selection of the available scholarly literature from the nonprofit management and evaluation discipline.

This literature review is not intended to be exhaustive of all material on the topic but identifies some key ideas related to the work of Invest In Open Infrastructure in building strong, resilient, responsive, and sustainable open infrastructure services supporting scientific and scholarly research. While often an overlooked feature of running a nonprofit organization, governance is key to ensuring services meet the current and future needs of those they serve in a way that delivers ongoing value in a regular, repeatable manner.

The following review is divided into four main sections, covering the definition of governance, including the conceptual and theoretical frameworks for understanding governance and the relationships involved, as well as the value of governance to establish the basis for understanding why governance is important; key governance practices as described in the literature; the structure and function of the board as the primary means by which governance is conducted; and the key models of governance demonstrating the range of options when creating a governance structure. We end with additional questions not covered in this review and a concluding paragraph to summarize the key points and discuss our future intentions with this work.

This is the beginning of our exploration, and we look forward to expanding our understanding of this important topic and sharing our future work, as well as additional resources and support, as through the conversations this work inspires and our continuing research into this important topic.

Note on Terminology and Scope

In this review, the phrase “served population” indicates the community that a nonprofit serves, while “community” signifies the community at large, primarily the community within the academic, scholarly, and library spaces. Although a few scholars (Carver, 2006) use the term CEO to address the main managerial position within nonprofit leadership, we will be using the term “Executive Director” or simply “executive” throughout this document for continuity and consistency across the literature described.

The term “nonprofit organization” is primarily a legal term meaning different things in different jurisdictions. Often referred to more broadly as the “third sector” or the “voluntary sector,” there are various conceptual definitions, particularly in the larger global context. Muukkonen (2009) reviews the definitions and their relationships to each other, including the idea of voluntary organizations, religious organizations, social movements, non-governmental organizations, nonprofits, the civil society, and various other organizing models.

In this review, we focus primarily on the nonprofit organization as constituted in the United States, though the literature cited does include case studies and research conducted in Europe as well as North America. We have attempted to focus on the key ideas and concepts that have applicability outside this limited legal frame rather than the nuances related to a particular geographical region. We acknowledge this does not take in the full sweep of nonprofit organizations and similarly constituted third sector organizations as they exist globally, and we look forward to further work expanding this perspective to include a broader understanding of the larger context for how this work takes place globally, particularly outside the North American and European contexts.

Defining Governance

Governance is “a conceptually coherent operating system or theory of the board’s role, position, practice, and relationships” (Carver, 2011, p. 376). Cornforth (2012) notes that there are various definitions of governance throughout several disciplines. The Latin origin of the word “governance” means “to direct or steer” (Cornforth, 2012). According to Cornforth (2012) and Cadbury’s (1992) definition of governance within the private sector is a system that administers and directs an organization.

Within the nonprofit sector, governance typically concentrates on the board and its actions (Cornforth, 2012). There is a consensus that governance includes elements like control and guidance of the organization along with the maintenance of

accountability guidelines (Cornforth, 2012). Therefore, Cornforth (2004) defines governance as “systems and processes concerned with ensuring the overall direction, control and accountability of an organization.” Bradshaw (2009) also discusses board governance and says that the board’s responsibilities include fiduciary duties, legal duties, onboarding and dismissing the executive director, safeguarding the mission, and creating and continuously evaluating the strategic plan.

The exact nature of this governance relationship between the board and the executive has been well explored in the literature. Jensen and Meckling (1976) describe this as a principal-agent relationship where one entity (the agent) supplies a service on behalf of another entity (the principal). In this capacity, the agent is given some level of authority to act in accordance with the principal’s interests (Van Puyvelde et al., 2012). The principal is responsible for establishing and maintaining sufficient accountability of the agent’s activities to ensure the agent is acting in the best interest of the principal, instead of in the agent’s own interest. To ensure the agent’s fidelity, the principal may offer incentives to the agent or ensure that the principal will be compensated if its goals are not met (Jensen & Meckling, 1976).

In the nonprofit governance relationship, either the board or the executive can fulfil the role of the principal with the other then filling the role of the agent. Determining this fundamental relationship is essential to the governance relationship that exists in an organization. Carver (2011) describes a relationship where the executive is principal, describing the board as the agent entity “on whose behalf the board governs” (p. 376). In contrast, Van Puyvelde, et al. (2012) and others describe the stakeholders in an organization, defined as the exogenous or endogenous individual or entity that impacts or is impacted by an organization, as the principal in this relationship, with the internal stakeholders, managers, staff, and volunteers, as agents of the principal’s interests (Lewis, 2001; Savage et al., 1991). In this way, the organization thus serves as a bridge between the external and internal stakeholders (Van Puyvelde et al., 2012).

A nonprofit’s relationship with numerous owners (or stakeholders), decision-making, goal-setting, and accountability are determined by many entities (Brody, 1996). In viewing the client (or served population) as an external stakeholder (sometimes described as the “stakeholder theory”), Van Puyvelde et al. (2012) assert that nonprofits have a greater opportunity than for-profit entities to build trust with the served population because the fulfilment of stakeholder needs is not incentivized solely by market forces but by other altruistic and values-based interests that center stakeholder needs in the mission of the organization.

Just being a legally constituted nonprofit organization is insufficient to generate and sustain trust, particularly in the long term. According to Moreno-Albarracín et al (2020), governance determines how the organization functions and the degree to which a community trusts and supports the organization. Transparency earns the organization trust and communal support (Moreno-Albarracín et. al., 2020). Such transparency demands quality outputs and outcomes for the served population, along with quality systems that produce such outcomes. These strong results help to solidify a favorable reputation within the community, which is important to attract funding, workers, volunteers, and other necessary resources and stakeholders that promote organizational longevity (Moreno-Albarracín et. al., 2020). An organization that is not perceived as legitimate encounters serious limitations in establishing relationships with critical stakeholders. Moreover, the loss/decline of legitimacy (due to e.g., bad image/reputation) is an element associated with closure and demise in nonprofits (Hager, 1999; Fernandez, 2008; Hernandez Ortiz, 2022). In other words, the loss of legitimacy due to e.g. insufficient accountability, deficient transparency, or conduct inconsistent with the interests of stakeholders, permitted by inadequate or poorly implemented governance structures, can severely damage if not threaten entirely the survival of the nonprofit organization.

Key Governance Practices

In their assessment of transparency and accountability, Moreno-Albarracín, et. al. (2020) list the most important factors that make a nonprofit trustworthy. They note the primacy of accountability through public disclosure of governing practices, policies, and procedures. Clearly stating these to both internal and external stakeholders is key in establishing expectations and ensuring fidelity to the mission in every action, which is vital to creating a strategic plan and is ultimately more important to the success of an organization than almost any other aspect of management. All other aspects of the organization, including planning, budgeting, and operations need to be in alignment with this mission in clear and consistent ways in order to cultivate trust.

With respect to the financial aspects of the organization, Moreno-Albarracín, et. al. (2020) describe the importance of making regular public disclosure of financial statements, including balance sheet, income statements, budgets, donation statements, and annual reports. Among these documents, the budget receives notable attention both in its preparation and in its application as signals of financial fidelity and accountability necessary for establishing and maintaining trust and transparency.

Moreno-Albarracín, et. al. (2020) further demonstrate that managers, staff, and volunteers build trust through their actions, particularly by maintaining good public

communication stakeholders through the use of effective bi-directional communication channels, including emails, newsletters, social media posts, a compliant system, and other means by which the organization is able to carry on a meaningful conversation with stakeholders beyond the minimum legal standards set by some jurisdictions.

Governance activities and practices are also crucial for encouraging diversity and inclusiveness within nonprofit organizations and between nonprofits and their stakeholders. Inclusive governance practices are usually initiated at the board level. As noted by Brown (2002), an 'inclusive board' recuperates input from multiple stakeholders, is aware of the needs of the community and clients the organization serves, and fosters regular contributions from stakeholders by establishing policies and procedures.

Board governance practices are influenced by the composition of the board. As noted by Buse et al. (2016), the composition of the board in terms of gender and racial/ethnic diversity influences the governance practices. Additionally, both inclusion practices (at the board level) and diversity policies and practices boost the diversity practices of the organization (Buse et al., 2016). In other words, board governance is benefited by a diverse board membership, especially in organizations that have put in place policies and practices that foster the input from members and stakeholders.

Specifically, in terms of gender, Dula et al. (2020) have studied the connection between female leaders and good governance in nonprofits. They have found that female board leadership has a positive impact on board performance. Specifically, a female board chair or a notable number of women on the board increases the governance performance on dimensions such as cultural, strategic and self-assessments.

Structure and Function of the Board

Governance is key to ensure that the principal's needs are met. BoardSource (2016) provides six elements for effective governance: board meetings, strategic planning, streamlined structure, the composition of the board and the staff, the leadership of the board and the organization, and the mission. Boardsource (2016) emphasizes the importance of addressing each of these elements consistently to the extent possible over time with flexibility, intention, and attention. An important and foundational aspect of a nonprofit board is that it is voluntary (Wright & Millesen, 2008). Voluntary board members are often professionals, tasked with legal responsibilities, fiduciary responsibilities, mission and vision fidelity, decision-making, policy production, goal setting, strategic planning, assessment of the Executive Director's performance,

evaluation of programmatic success or failure, and budgetary performance to ensure accountability (Wright & Millesen, 2008; LeRoux & Langer, 2016).

Although these duties belong to the board, the Executive Director is usually the person with the necessary information, expertise, and resources to provide organizational leadership (Wright & Millesen, 2008). Wright and Millesen (2008) also address the relationship between the board and the executive. The executive often contributes to the development of the board and also has a role in holding them accountable. In this manner, the board and the executive evaluate each other's performance. Considering these factors, not all boards adequately accomplish their designated tasks (Wright & Millesen, 2008; LeRoux & Langer, 2016) and ambiguities about board member roles can adversely impact the performance of the board and the organization as a whole (Wright & Millesen, 2008).

Van Puyvelde et al. (2012) make clear the value of the board is best realized with representative governance where clients, or at least their interests, are well-represented if not physically present in the deliberations of the board. This increases the likelihood that the needs will be met and increases the nonprofit's accountability to the served population.

In representative governance, those in governance roles are representatives of larger stakeholder interests rather than their own individual interests, similar to representative governance models in liberal democracies (Piscitelli & Geobey, 2020). According to Piscitelli and Geobey (2020), a representative board member¹ is one who joins a board with the intention of representing the concerns of a particular constituency or stakeholder. This type of governance incorporates issues of diversity, equity, and inclusion into governance practices.

Piscitelli and Geobey (2020) state that as long as the representative is ethical and abides by the expectations of the position, the representative's voice can echo the needs of the client, granting the board greater insight in decision-making and leveraging client loyalty. Because of these benefits, the representative board member should not only be present on the board but should be valued. The representative's voice, opinions, and concerns should be considered and integrated into both the governance and managerial processes (Piscitelli & Geobey, 2020). Such inclusion is an example of good governance, according to Piscitelli and Geobey (2020), and highlights the principal-agent relationship between the client and the organization.

¹ Described as a "director" in the Piscitelli and Geobey, the term "board member" is used here for clarity.

It is important to note that a representative board member must be willing to add representation to the standard duties of board membership, instead of only serving for the representative agenda (Piscitelli & Geobey, 2020). When a director joins the board with an agenda, complications can occur. Piscitelli and Geobey (2020) cite Houle's (1990) warnings, particularly the admonition that a board member whose primary reason for membership is to concentrate on a handful of issues may not sufficiently contribute. In this situation, the other members must accommodate for the inadequacy. Another echoed by Piscitelli and Geobey is that a board member with limited interest or specific motives may be inequitable in their judgements or may use their voice to obtain unethical advantages. In this scenario, ego and a lack of ethics coexist, producing bad governance and tainting the principal-agent relationship.

Effective governance of a nonprofit organization is not possible without trust, transparency, and accountability. The reviewed literature discusses transparency as an element of trust, and in the principal-agent relationship, both are crucial. Miller (2002) asserts that it is the board's job to monitor the executive's work, to keep the executive accountable to the principal's desires, and to ensure that the principal's desires are being met. Moreno-Albarracín, et. al. (2020) indicates explicitly that good governance and transparency are partners that produce legitimacy for a nonprofit. These partners also bolster the trust that encourages donors to fund the organization, therefore producing organizational longevity (Moreno-Albarracín et al., 2020).

Models of Governance

While all governance structures share the qualities outlined above, there are a range of models for how governance is carried out. Bradshaw (2009) advocates for a "contingency approach" in determining the correct model that takes into account the organization's exogenous stakeholders, including funders, donors, clients, and organizational partnerships to determine the correct model of governance. Other contingencies mentioned are ideology, size, age of the organization, and strategy and structure. According to Bradshaw (2009), external environments can be thought of as simple or complex depending on the variety of stakeholder interests from comparatively small and relatively homogenous (in the case of simple external environments) or more numerous and heterogenous (in the case of more complex external environments). Bradshaw (2009) also describes environments as being either relatively stable and certain or turbulent and uncertain to the point of being chaotic. Each type of environment necessitates a different model or at least approach to governance that acknowledges this environment and allows the organization to respond appropriately to it.

Piscitelli & Geobey (2020) discuss the relevance of board size for understanding the function of the board in governance. Smaller nonprofits with smaller boards may have a model where their directors are more heavily involved in management and in the operations of the organization as volunteers in service delivery. Governance, in these situations, may take a back seat to management. Nonprofits with larger boards have more room to choose whether board members will focus on governance or be simultaneously involved in management.

We discuss three primary traditional models of governance below, including the policy board model, the executive-centered board model, and the board-centered model, with additional reflections from Bradshaw (2009) on the external conditions these best address.² Each describes in more detail the actual functioning of the board in the organization with respect to the executive and is a useful guide as organizations are determining the model of governance they wish to cultivate.

The Policy Board Model

In the policy model described by Carver (2011), the board assumes almost all of the governance activities of the organization, providing a centralized form of governance in the board with clear relationships between the board and the executive as well as between the board and the community (Nathan Garber and Associates, n.d.). In this model the board is responsible for defining organizational policies and governing principles, assigning responsibility for implementing these policies and principles, assessing adherence to these policies and principles, and holding board members and staff accountable for their actions (Nathan Garber and Associates, n.d.).

Because the board cannot handle executive responsibilities alone, or at least not without great difficulty, Carver (2011) suggests the Executive Director should be a bridge between the board's broad leadership and the day-to-day management of staff by creating a system through which staff activities are smoothly coordinated to realize the policy goals and vision established by the board. Carver (2011) states that because of the board's primary leadership role, the board broadly decides the organization's impact on the community, but should provide staff maximum latitude whenever possible to carry out the policies of the board.

Board development is key in the policy board model, with board members being selected for their connection to the mission and educated over time as to their role in the organization (Nathan Garber and Associates, n.d.). Carver (2011) asserts that board members should become more adept at governing while the executive simultaneously

² Bradshaw (2009) doesn't address the executive-centered model so there are no reflections on the external environments this model best addresses.

becomes more adept at management. Key to this model is keeping the distinct roles in balance. If the executive's management skills surpass the board's governing skills, the board risks having its authority undermined as the executive picks up the slack and assumes more governing responsibilities from the board. Carver (2011) compares this situation to that of a well-aware child smoothly leading an immature parent and taking on their parenting responsibilities.

According to Bradshaw (2009), this model, which she refers to as the "policy governance" model, is best for boards where the organization's exogenous environment is stable and uncomplicated. In these situations, the board composition is often more homogenous, with the board structure and committees standardized by agendas and requirements. The hierarchical relationship between the executive and the board is well-established and unquestioned with little incentive toward change. This is the model preferred by organizations with larger boards.

The Executive-Centered Model

According to Herman and Heimovics (1990), the executive-centered model makes the executive's leadership central for organizational governance, with the executive actively engaging with board members to shape board practices and outcomes, as well as the overarching structure of the board, including scheduling board meetings, defining the purpose of committees, and translating goals into achievable tasks by the board. The executive is also responsible for providing the information necessary to make decisions, including programmatic data, budgetary reports, and financial statements, keeping the board informed of changes in the organization's internal and external environment. The executive emboldens the board to engage new opportunities, new ideas, and better methods of accomplishing the mission. The executive director sets standards for the board, while communicating with the president and committee chairs to inspire the board's timely completion of tasks.

As described by Herman and Heimovics (1990), rather than the board developing and defining its work independently of the executive, as in the policy board model, the executive drives the work of the board, often facilitating the exchange of views and perspectives towards the building of consensus among board members, and ensuring the board members have productive interactions with each other and with the executive.

Herman and Heimovics (1990) warn that in the executive-centered model the executive needs to delegate authority and obligation to staff so the increased focus on governance doesn't detract from the fulfilment of necessary management functions the executive is also responsible for. Unlike in the policy board model where the board

is helping articulate the value of the organization in the community, the executive has a number of external-facing responsibilities, such as creating and maintaining reciprocal and healthy relationships with funders, foundations, professional groups, government agencies, and nonprofits as part of their governance work.

The Board-Centered Model

The board-centered model described by LeRoux & Langer 2016 focuses on the fiduciary responsibilities and strategic roles of the board, emphasizing the working relationship between the board and management and the role that relationship plays on the organization's effectiveness. Although some scholars believe that the policy board fits within the board-centered model (Bernstein, 2007), LeRoux & Langer (2016) claim that the board-centered model fits between the policy model and the executive-centered model with the two models defining opposing ends of a continuum between board independence in governance under the policy board model and executive dominance in the executive-centered model. Chait, Ryan, and Taylor's (2005) further develop this idea in their Governance by Leadership model where they describe an approach where the Executive Director articulates the organization's foundation, including the vision, mission, values, and culture. Within this model, the board is present for financial matters, strategic matters, and generative matters, and the board and the executive work in tandem. According to Bernstein (2007), Governance by Leadership affirms the board's role in managerial endeavors and is best understood as an example of a board-centered model.

In the board-centered model, the board is highly engaged outside of standard governance activities, including being responsive to staff needs when the organization is in crisis (Bernstein, 2007), performing field research when the organization is experiencing an existential change, and actively engaging with stakeholders as part of their deliberations (Chait et al., 2005). Not limited to governance, they are more directly involved in the accomplishment of the organization's mission and goals. Chait et al. (2005) describe the benefit of not limiting the board's presence in the boardroom, which constrains their access to nuances that impact their served population by leaving them without "cues and clues" to perform their necessary function, as well as opening channels information about the organization's activities outside those managed by the executive.

Being on a continuum between the policy board and the executive-centered board, Bradshaw (2009) refers to this model as the "entrepreneurial" or "corporate" model when the organization is in an uncertain or chaotic external environment but has a simple group of stakeholders. This model is less formal in its policies. Action is emphasized over bureaucratic processes, so there may be more task forces and not as

many committees. Roles and responsibilities are not as stringently defined as they are in policy governance and representative governance. Board composition is more heterogeneous in the entrepreneurial model. There is less centralization, and efficiency is deemed important. These nonprofits may have smaller boards. Strategic planning occurs in collaboration between the board and the staff.

When the stakeholders are numerous and the environment is more unstable, Bradshaw (2009) describes this as an “emergent cellular model” with an even less developed hierarchy of committees or task forces assigned to pertinent issues as needed. The structure is often highly dynamic, with a small, diverse board that may value causes that are considered unconventional.

Further Questions to Explore

The exercise of creating governance structures is an important one but how an organization actually goes about creating those structures in cooperation with stakeholders isn't covered in this literature review and deserves further study. Additionally, the process by which an organization can best go about thoughtfully and transparently recruiting, interviewing, and appointing board members to ensure diverse interests are well-represented is an area that needs further study in order to provide practical advice to nonprofit organizations aspiring to a high level of accountability, diversity, and trustworthiness in their governance structures and processes. It is essential that meaningful signals be sent to the community that their interests as principal are being represented by the organization and with further research, we hope to help describe those signals in future work.

Conclusion

As demonstrated in the literature described above, there is no one right way to structure governance for a nonprofit organization. There are a variety of models with strengths and weaknesses for an organization to consider. An organization is also embedded in an external environment and internal context that makes the selection of a governance model highly contingent, and the model that works best now may not in the near future. To realize the value of governance, these factors must all be considered for how they help the organization achieve their mission and vision by honestly acknowledging their situation, communicating their intentions, and then holding themselves accountable to their stakeholders to abide by the governance practices they put in place.

As we build a more resilient, reliable, and sustainable infrastructure of open tools and technology services supporting scientific research, scholarly communication, and

information management, this type of work is essential to ensuring the services not only deliver value but also do so in a way that is aligned with the needs and interests of the larger community we seek to serve. We look forward to expanding on this work as the state of learning about governance practices in the nonprofit sector advances and our understanding of how those practices relate to the management of open infrastructure services also advances. We will continue having conversations about this work and learning from those practising these principles to learn more about what we know and still need to discover to ensure our services are well governed to meet current and future challenges towards a shared vision of open infrastructure as the default in science, scholarship, and information management globally.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Dr. Elizabeth Searing and Dr. Allison Russell for providing early feedback on this work.

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